

The Impact of Mechanical Treatment of the Al_2O_3 Nanomatrices Surface on their Optical Parameters with and without KDP Crystals Inclusion

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The optical properties of Al_2O_3 nanocrystalline matrices without filling the pores and with the pores filled with water-soluble KDP, ADP, and KB5 crystals were studied by us in [1]. However, we did not examine the state of the surface of Al_2O_3 nanomatrices, as well as its effect on the optical characteristics of these matrices. This thesis presents the results of surface roughness measurements of Al_2O_3 nanomatrices manufactured by the German company Smartmembranes. The surface roughness was measured using a Diktak II profilometer of the Sloan company (USA). The measured data are depicted in Fig 1. After a series of conducted measurements, it was established that the roughness of the surface of the Al_2O_3 nanoporous matrices depends on the method of obtaining the original Al aluminum sheets with a thickness of 100-200 microns.

a)

b)

Fig. 1. Surface roughness of the samples with the inclusion of the KDP crystals (a) before and (b) after the mechanical treatment

In addition, in the thesis, we measured the optical characteristics of nanoporous Al_2O_3 matrices before and after mechanical treatment. Optical characteristics of nanoporous matrices for different pore diameters were measured on a Shimadzu-3600 spectrophotometer.

Analogous measurements of the optical characteristics of nanoporous Al_2O_3 matrices with the inclusion of KDP crystals inside the pores were carried out before and after the mechanical treatment of the surface. Since KDP crystals are water-soluble, ethyl alcohol was used as a liquid to prepare the polishing suspension.

The performed studies show a significant effect of the surfaces of nanoporous Al_2O_3 matrices on the optical characteristics, both with the inclusion of KDP crystals inside the pores and without. Thus, to eliminate the effect of roughness on the surfaces of nanoporous Al_2O_3 matrices and receive higher optical characteristics with both empty and filled pores, it is suggested to use their mechanical processing (grinding and polishing).

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[1] N. Andrushchak, et al., 2021 IEEE 11th International Conference Nanomaterials: Applications & Properties (NAP), 2021, pp. 1-5.